

Short communication

Report of cabbage stem weevil, *Ceutorhynchus pallidactylus* (Col.: Curculionidae) on oilseed rape from Iran

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چکیده

در بررسی آفات کلزا در منطقه‌ی مرودشت استان فارس، در نیمه‌ی فروردین ۱۳۸۷، ساقه‌های آفت‌زده حاوی لارو و تخم‌های مشکوک به سرخرطومی مشاهده و جمع‌آوری گردید. جهت دستیابی به حشرات کامل، لاروهای آفت در آزمایشگاه پرورش داده شد. این سرخرطومی با نام علمی (*Ceutorhynchus pallidactylus* (Marsham) (= *C. quadridens* Panzer) (Col.: Curculionidae) شناسایی و توسط پروفسور Alziar Gabriel مورد تأیید قرار گرفت. این گونه برای اولین بار از ایران گزارش می‌شود.

During the study of oilseed rape pests in Marvdasht area (Fars province), the infested stems of the crop to weevil eggs and larvae were collected at April 2008. The larvae were reared at laboratory conditions until adult weevils emerged. The weevils were identified as cabbage stem weevil, *Ceutorhynchus pallidactylus* (Marsham) (= *C. quadridens* Panzer) (Col.: Curculionidae), and confirmed by Alziar Gabriel. This species has been reported as a pest of oilseed rape in many European countries such as Poland, former Czechoslovakia, Germany, UK, Austria and Switzerland as well as North Africa, America, Canada and Russia (Barari, 2005). Herewith, the species is reported for first time from Iran.

The adult of *C. pallidactylus* is 2.5 - 3.5 mm long, grayish-brown with scattered grayish-white scales all over the body and fine hairs on the elytra with those concentrated centrally on the base of elytra making a white rectangular spot (Jourdeuil, 1963). The beak is thin and is located under head toward coxae. The tarsi and tibia have a brown-red colour. The egg is oval, smooth, shiny, and translucent, 0.7 mm long and 0.6 mm wide (Jourdeuil, 1963; Alford, 1999). Its legless larva is 4-6 mm long with a white elongated body and light-yellow head capsule (Jourdeuil, 1963; Kirk, 1992).

The eggs are laid in the leaves and petioles. Oviposition holes on the plant tissues are the first symptoms of damage on the crop. The larvae feed inside petioles and stems, which had negative effect on plant grow and reduce number of seeds and yield (Ferguson *et al.*, 2003). When fully developed, the larvae leave the plants drop to the soil into which they burrow to pupate (Alford *et al.*, 2003). In severe infestation, especially after heavy raining and cold

weather, stem diseases such as stem canker (*Leptosphaeria maculans* – anamorph: *Phoma lingam*) could be problematic and contribute to yield loss (Broschewitz & Daebeler, 1987).

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